

Multifunctional structural energy storage composites

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Background

- Multifunctional structural energy storage devices, such as batteries and supercapacitors, have attracted keen interest owing to their potential for weight and volume reductions at system level and improved safety [1-3].
- One of the biggest challenges in this field is to maintain excellent (ideally the same as existing structure of the same weight) mechanical properties while storing adequate electrical energy. To this end, structural energy storage structures with both outstanding mechanical properties and electrical energy storage performance are highly desirable [4-8].

Fig.1 Carbon fibre-based honeycomb core structure supercapacitors.

Fig.2 Carbon fibre-based sandwich structure batteries

Project Aims

- In this project, new structural concepts for composite batteries will be developed to store electrical energy, without sacrificing mechanical strength and stiffness. Examples include designing new energy storage cores for sandwich structures using either supercapacitor or laminated battery techniques.
- The research reported in this paper focuses on a sandwich structure design for a structural supercapacitor. As illustrated in Fig.1, a honeycomb core will be first made by 3D printing from either an epoxy resin or thermoplastic polymer.
- A mixture of ionic liquid and lithium salt will be injected into the core, followed by bonding to two carbon fibre composite facesheets to form a structurally strong sandwich structure containing an electrolyte of high ionic conductivity.
- The combination of the honeycomb core and the electrolyte provides a structure that is both stiff and ionically conductive. In addition, structurally strong and stiff laminated composite batteries will be developed by incorporating ionically conductive materials, such as silica nanoparticles and ionic liquid, into a solid polymer electrolyte to manufacture composite structures with high ionic conductivity and mechanical stiffness.
- The sandwich structure in Fig.2 will be used to develop composite batteries or supercapacitors with excellent mechanical and energy storage properties.